

An Insight into the Employee Stress Level Prevailing at SAIL-SCL Kerala Limited

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Abstract

Today's workplace is global, fast-paced and technology-driven. It takes the bright minds of smart employees for business to maintain a competitive edge. Satisfied and highly motivated and loyal employees represent the basis of competitive company. The growth of satisfaction is to be reflected in the increase of productivity, improvement of the products' quality or rendered services and higher number of innovations. This study focuses on employee's stress level and stress management. On top of that, it would provide valuable information to the organization in understanding the problem. Iron and Steel industry in India is on an upswing owing to the presence of a strong global and domestic demand. Steel Authority of India Limited (SAIL) is the largest steel-making company in India and one of the seven Maharatna's of the country's Central Public Sector Enterprises. This study result will help the company to know the extent of stress that they are facing and how they react to it and also it helps to improve the stress management practice of SAIL-SCL Kerala Limited.

Keywords: Iron and Steel industry, Employees stress level, Stress management.

Introduction

Iron and Steel industry in India is on an upswing because of the strong global and domestic demand. India's rapid economic growth and soaring demand by sectors like infrastructure, real estate and automobiles, at home and abroad, has put Indian steel industry on the global map. India was the world's third-largest steel producer in 2016. As the growth in the Indian steel sector has been driven by domestic availability of raw materials such as iron ore and cost-effective labor. Consequently, the steel sector has been a major contributor to India's manufacturing output. In addition to this, increasing GDP and the expectedly growing urban infrastructure, roads and highways, railways etc. to be the key focus areas and will take necessary steps to achieve the same by diverting consumers focus from non-steel intensive to steel intensive products.

Steel Authority of India Limited (SAIL) is the largest steel-making company in India and one of the seven Maharatna's of the country's Central Public Sector Enterprises. SAIL manufactures and

sells a wide variety of steel products such as hot and cold rolled sheets and coils, galvanized sheets, electrical sheets, structural, railway products, plates, bars and rods, stainless steel and other alloy steels. It also produces long and flat steel products, which is in demand in the domestic as well in international market.

The employees stress level and stress management at SAIL-SCL Kerala Limited such as training practices, recognition programs, cordial relation with superiors and co-workers etc. helped to reduce the stress level of employees.

Here through this study on “Employees Stress Level and Stress Management at SAIL-SCL Kerala Limited” an attempt is made to understand the stress management practices of SAIL-SCL Kerala Limited.

Review of Literature

Employees are valuable assets of an organization and the key to success. Employers need to understand that a content and motivated employee has a higher probability of making significant contributions to the organization. In this context, it is very important to review prior research studies conducted in the area of employees stress and stress management. The review of prior research studies reveals that the presence of stress in work is almost inevitable in all organization. Many prior studies were revealing that stress is a widespread phenomenon and it's a part of normal life of an employee and it should be reduced by giving various programs like vocational tours, cultural programs, sports, classes for yoga and meditations, meeting, and counseling to the employees and organization is responsible authority for reducing the stress of their employees. The review of literature were pointing out some facts i.e., male employees are more stressed than the female employees, stress affects the human brain, its functioning, because the brain's ability to function is closely correlated with the emotional state, stressful situation at work place, disturbs the mental peace, weakens a person psychologically and creates complexities in social and familial relationship, people with a higher percentage of occupational stress may not be satisfied with their job and therefore they will not feel happy working in the organization, and organizational culture, role and responsibility that are responsible for stress and stress has an effect on job performance. Finally, the review of prior studies indicates that high stress will cause decrease in the commitment of employees towards the organization and their work. Hence this research study is focusing on work commitment level of employees, physical, emotional, intellectual and behavioral aspects of stress among employee, and the effects of stress among the employees in SAIL-SCL Kerala Limited.

Statement of the Problem

In 1985-86 the company made a profit of 3.97 crore. But later due to the impacts in the international steel/scrap market, profit came down in 1987-88. Afterwards SAIL-SCL Kerala Limited again ran into loss. To bring back the financial position on a correct track, in 1992 SAIL-SCL Kerala Limited made a reference to the board for Industrial and Financial construction. IDBI was appointed as an operative agency to explore the revival program. In 1993 the employees sacrificed by reducing manpower strength and agreeing for freezing salary and other benefits. Due to various reasons the BIFR scheme failed. On the verge of collapse they stuck with a correct decision to involve with SAIL in the revival scheme of SCL. From these circumstantial evidences it is very evident about the quantum of stress that the employees have been passing through over the past decades. This study is intended to identify the stress level of employees and the stress management practices adopted by SAIL-SCL Kerala Limited.

Scope of the Study

The scope of the study is restricted to understand the stress level of employees presently working at SAIL-SCL Kerala Limited and to analyze into the various stress management practices they would utilize.

Objectives of the Study

- To understand the work commitment level of employees at SAIL-SCL Kerala Limited.
- To understand the physical, emotional, intellectual and behavioral aspects of stress among employee at SAIL-SCL Kerala Limited.
- To understand the effects of stress among the employees in the organization.

Hypotheses of the Study

1. There is no significant relation between the emotional, intellectual, and behavioral aspects of stress among employees.
2. There is no significant difference between various categories of respondents towards work commitment.

Methodology of the Study

In this study research design used is descriptive research; both the secondary and primary data were used for the purpose of this study. Primary data has been collected from the employees of SAIL-SCL Kerala Limited, by circulating an interview schedule among the employees of SAIL-SCL Kerala Limited. The secondary data were collected from prior research thesis-published and unpublished thesis, research articles, SAIL-SCL Kerala Limited company website-www.steelcomplexkerala.com, brochures provided from SAIL-SCL Kerala Limited, Annual Report of SAIL-SCL Kerala Limited.

Tools Used for Data Collection and Analysis

A well structured questionnaire was used to collect data from the employees of administration and factory. SPSS 25th version is used to coding and analyzing the data. Descriptive statistics like percentage mean score, std. deviation and inferential statistics like independent sample t-test, Pearson correlation and z-score percentile methods were used to bring out the result.

Limitations of the Study

1. Higher amount of time is required for collecting information from each employee.
2. Some of the respondents were not co-operative with the survey.

Analysis and Discussion

1. The study result indicates that 47 per cent of the respondents are in the age group of above 50 years.
2. Study found that 80 per cent of the respondents are male.
3. Out of the samples taken majority of the employees have an experience of more than 20 years.
4. Study result indicates that 37 per cent of the respondents opine that, organization focus on employee care and their empowerment.
5. According to the survey conducted 63 per cent of the employee's state that the organization takes necessary steps to manage stress.
6. It was found that 100 per cent of the respondents don't feel any physical inconvenience due to job related stress.

7. It was found that 93 per cent of the respondent's states that stress do not influence their job performance.
8. It is inferred from the study that 43 per cent of the employees manage stress by listening to music.
9. Most of the employees agree that they never had arguments with their supervisors and co-workers.
10. It is found that majority (49 per cent) of the respondents recommend that Realistic goal setting, Physiological fitness, yoga or meditations are the best method for preventing stress

Classification of Response Based on Work Commitment Factors

The employees of SAIL had responded to the various work commitment factors given to them. The response of the employee's work commitment factors is given in the table 1

Table 1
Classification of Response Based on Work Commitment Factors– Descriptive Statistics

Work Commitment	Employees	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
	Administrative	40	3.6923	.51442	.01267
	Factory Worker	20	4.2132	.50862	.01485

Source: Primary Data

Table 1 indicates that both factory and administrative employees have agreed with the work commitment and the std. deviation is almost equally disbursed. Hence it could be seen that majority of the respondents are positively respond about various work commitment factors. The std. error mean is very small in case of factory workers and administrative employees, hence, it can be inferred that the Mean score is actually representing the total population mean

Table 2
Classification of Response Based on Work Commitment Factors

Independent Samples Test				
Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		F	2.330	
		Sig.	.132	
Equal variances assumed	t-test for Equality of Means	t	-2.998	
		df	58	
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.004	
		Mean Difference	-.825	
		Std. Error Difference	.275	
		95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	Lower	-1.376
			Upper	-.274
Equal variances not assumed	t-test for Equality of Means	t	-3.372	
		df	51.624	
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.001	
		Mean Difference	-.825	
		Std. Error Difference	.245	
		95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	Lower	-1.316
			Upper	-.334

Source: Primary Data

Table 2 shows independent sample t-test result to find whether there is any significant difference between the opinion of factory workers and administrative employees regarding various work commitment factors. Levene’s Test for Equality of Variances p-value is .132 i.e., $.132 > 0.05$ and $F=2.330$, hence it can be inferred that the group variance are equal, therefore equal variance assumed was used to interpret the further result. The test result indicates that p-value is lesser at 5 per cent significant level i.e., $t(58)=-2.998$, $p\text{-value}=.004 < 0.05$, hence it could be concludes that the null hypothesis is there is no significant difference between factory workers and administrative employees opinion regarding work commitment factors stands rejected.

Classification of Respondents Based on Various Stress Triggering Factors

Table 3
Classification of Respondents Based on Various Stress Triggering Factors

Emotional	Pearson Correlation	.862**	1	.770**	.684**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000	.007
	N	60	60	60	60
Intellectual	Pearson Correlation	.918**	.770**	1	.723**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000		.000
	N	60	60	60	60
Behavioral	Pearson Correlation	.675**	.684**	.723**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.007	.000	
	N	60	60	60	60

Source: Primary Data, **. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 3 shows the Pearson correlation test result to identify the correlation among the variables in related to employees stress. Here the result indicates that Pearson correlation p-value is lesser at 5 per cent significant level in related to Phy., emotional, intellectual and behavioral factors and the correlation test values are above 0.6, hence it can be inferred that the correlation is strong and found that there is a significant relationship between the factors like emotional, intellectual and behavioral aspects of stress among employees

Table 4
Respondents Preference towards Stress Management Tool

Stress Management Tool	W-Score	M Score	Z-score	Z-score %	Rank
Flexible Working Hours	390	6.50	1.215	88.79	Rank 2
Regular Medical Check up	248	4.14	-0.698	24.24	Rank 8
Counseling Programs	364	6.06	0.949	82.87	Rank 4
Trainings	357	5.96	0.606	72.79	Rank 5
Regular Interaction with Mgt.	355	5.92	0.989	83.86	Rank 3
Motivational Talks	290	4.84	-0.197	42.17	Rank 7
Financial Support	475	7.91	2.615	99.55	Rank 1
Risk Avoidance at Workplace	307	5.11	0.099	53.96	Rank 6
Recognition Programs	174	2.89	-3.222	0.06	Rank 9

Source: Primary Data

Table 4 shows the respondents ranking preference regarding stress management tools. Z-score percentile method was used to find the respondents preference. Result indicates that 99.55 per cent of respondents are given first rank to financial support (Rank 1) as a stress management tool, second rank is given to flexible working hours (88.79 per cent, Rank 2), third rank is given to Regular Interaction with Mgt (83.96 per cent, Rank 3). Finally the last rank is given to Recognition Programs (0.06 per cent, Rank 9)

Conclusion

Stress is the “wear and tear” of human bodies caused by frequently changing environment. It has both physical and emotional effects. It can create positive or negative feelings. Stress has become a major concern of the modern times as it can cause harm to employee’s health and performance. Much of stress at work is caused not only by work overload and time pressure but also by lack of rewards and praise, and more importantly, by not providing individuals with the autonomy to do their work as they would like. In this era, it is important to maintain a proper stress management tools in an organization which can make a stimulus in employees.

From this study we can say that, SAIL-SCL Kerala Limited is providing an ample working atmosphere to the employees. The best way to improve their stress management practice is to develop a good communication among the workers and employers, provide the employees with productive working hours, job security etc..

From the T-test conducted it was found that the work commitment level of the administration level employees was less than that of the factory workers. And the main outcome of the correlation analysis was that there exists a strong positive relationship between the factors like emotional, intellectual and behavioral aspects of stress among employees. This indicates that emotional, intellectual and behavioral aspects of employees are significantly related to stress.

From the study it was found that most of the employees are not having much stress related to their job, as there is no much production happening in the company. But at this circumstance, they are not satisfied with the financial support provided by the company. Hence the Marginal Propensity to consume for these workers are less when compared to other workers in other organization. So the only stress that the employees face within the organization is regarding the financial support.

SAIL-SCL Kerala Limited is providing suitable steps to manage the employees stress and those are very much useful to them. This will lead to work commitment of the employees and finally helps the organization to achieve its goal.

Suggestions

1. Since the employees don’t feel stressed and they are having a positive atmosphere within the organization the company must try to maintain that.
2. The employees have a positive response that the organization allows them to take part in the decision making and also consider their views and ideas. So the organization must try to maintain this, so that the employees will have a positive feeling that they are a part of the organization which will help to improve their work commitment.
3. The work commitment of the administration staff can be improved by providing them training and finding out what is the problem that they are facing in the organization.
4. If the company provides a better financial support to their employees, it will help to reduce their stress, as a sense of stability and safety will build within the employees.
5. Initiatives need to taken wherein the company can make sure the employees are not sitting idle, which can be attained once the production is happening in full swing.

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